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Research Article

**A STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD
DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR SIMULTANEOUS
ESTIMATION OF MONTELUKAST AND FEXOFENADINE
HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL
DOSAGE FORM****Dr. Gampa Vijay Kumar¹, Dr.T.Rajesh², Jaya Chandhra³**

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Abstract

A new method was established for simultaneous estimation of Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast by using Xterra C18 5 μ m (4.6*250mm) column, flow rate was 1ml/min, mobile phase ratio was Phosphate buffer (0.05M) pH 4.6: ACN (55:45%v/v) (pH was adjusted with orthophosphoric acid), detection wave length was 255nm. The instrument used was Shimadzu, model No. SPD-20MA LC+20AD, Software- LC-20 Solution. The retention times were found to be 2.399mins and 3.907mins. The % purity of Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast was found to be 100.7% and 101.4% respectively. The system suitability parameters for Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 1.3, 5117.5 and 1.4, 3877.3 the resolution was found to be 8.0. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study for Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast was found in concentration range of 1 μ g-5 μ g and 100 μ g-500 μ g and correlation coefficient (r²) was found to be 0.999 and 0.999, % mean recovery was found to be 100% and 100.5%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.2 and 0.4, % RSD for intermediate precision was 0.5 and 0.1 respectively. The precision study was precise, robust, and repeatable. LOD value was 2.95 and 3.04, and LOQ value was 9.87 and 10 respectively.

Keyword: Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast, RP-HPLC method

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INTRODUCTION:

Fexofenadine, sold under the trade name Allegra among others is an antihistamine pharmaceutical drug used in the treatment of allergy symptoms, such as hay fever and urticaria. Therapeutically, fexofenadine is a selective peripheral H₁-blocker. Fexofenadine is classified as a second-generation antihistamine because it is less able to pass the blood-brain barrier and cause sedation, compared to first-generation antihistamines. It has also been called a third-generation antihistamine, although there is some controversy associated with the use of the term

Fexofenadine

Montelukast (trade name Singulair) is a leukotriene receptor antagonist (LTRA) used for the maintenance treatment of asthma and to relieve symptoms of seasonal allergies. Montelukast comes as a tablet, a chewable tablet, and granules to take by mouth. Montelukast is usually taken once a day with or without food.^[4] Montelukast is a CysLT₁ antagonist; it blocks the action of leukotriene D₄ (and secondary ligands LTC₄ and LTE₄) on the cysteinyl leukotriene receptor CysLT₁ in the lungs and bronchial tubes by binding to it. This reduces the bronchoconstriction otherwise caused by the leukotriene and results in less inflammation.

Montelukast**MATERIALS AND METHOD AND INSTRUMENTATION:**

HPLC Shimadzu, model No. SPD-20MA LC+20AD, Software- LC-20 Solution UV double beam UV 3000 UV Win 5 Lab India Digital weighing pH meter Ultra sonicator Suction pump. Fexofenadine HCl and Montelukast, Potassium dihydrogen, Acetonitrile, Methanol, Water.

Chromatographic conditions**Trial-5:****Chromatographic conditions:**

Column	:	Xterra C18 5µm (4.6*250mm)
Mobile phase ratio	:	Phosphate buffer (0.05M) pH 4.6: ACN (55:45% v/v)
Detection wavelength	:	255nm
Flow rate	:	1ml/min Injection
volume	:	20µl Column
temperature	:	Ambient

Fig. 1 Chromatogram of Trail-5

Table 1 Details of Trail-5

S.No	Peak name	Rt	Area	Height	USP count	Plate	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Fexofenadine Hcl	2.499	945134	156429	5104		1.2	7.1
2	Montelukast	3.806	112541	13839	3787		1.3	

OBSERVATON:

The chromatogram is perfect with clear separation of components. The peak symmetry and system suitability parameters are within the limits. Hence this method is chosen as optimized one

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE SOLUTIONS: *For preparation of 50% solution (With respect to target Assay concentration):*

Accurately 5mg of Montelukast and 5mg of Fexofenadine Hcl working standard were weighed and transferred into a 10mL and 100ml of clean dry volumetric flask and about 7mL of Diluents was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock Solution). Further 3ml and 0.3ml of the above Montelukast and Fexofenadine Hcl stock solution were pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

For preparation of 100% solution (With respect to target Assay concentration):

Accurately 10mg of Montelukast and 10mg of

Fexofenadine Hcl working standard were weighed and transferred into a 10mL and 100ml of clean dry volumetric flask and about 7mL of Diluents was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock Solution). Further 3ml and 0.3ml of the above Montelukast and Fexofenadine Hcl stock solution were pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

For preparation of 150% solution (With respect to target Assay concentration):

Accurately 15mg of Montelukast and 15mg of Fexofenadine Hcl working standard were weighed and transferred into a 10mL and 100ml of clean dry volumetric flask and about 7mL of Diluents was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock Solution). Further 3ml and 0.3ml of the above Montelukast and Fexofenadine Hcl stock solution were pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

METHOD VALIDATION:**Accuracy:****Preparation of standard solution (Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast):**

Accurately weighed 10 mg of Montelukast and 10mg of Fexofenadine Hcl working standard were transferred into a 10mL and 100ml of clean dry volumetric flasks.

About 7mL and 70ml of Diluents are added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

PRECISION:**A) Repeatability: Preparation of standard stock solution:**

Accurately 10 mg of Montelukast and 10mg of Fexofenadine Hcl working standard were weighed and transferred into a 10mL and 100ml of clean dry volumetric flasks and about 7mL and 70ml of Diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

INTERMEDIATE PRECISION**(Ruggedness):**

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as ruggedness) of the method, precision was performed on different days by using different make column of same dimensions.

Specificity:

The system suitability for specificity was carried out to determine whether there is any interference of any impurities in retention time of analytical peak. The specificity was performed by injecting blank.

LOD:

LOD's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) at levels approximating the LOD according to the formula. The standard

deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

LOQ:

LOQ's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) according to the formula. Again, the standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y- intercepts of regression lines.

LINEARITY:**Preparation of stock solution:**

Accurately 10 tablets were weighed & crushed in mortar and pestle and weight equivalent to 10 mg of Montelukast and Fexofenadine Hcl (marketed formulation) sample were transferred into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and about 7mL of Diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

Range:

Based on precision, linearity and accuracy data it can be concluded that the assay method is precise, linear and accurate in the range of 1µg- 5µg and 100µg- 500µg of Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast respectively.

Robustness:

As part of the robustness, deliberate change in the flow rate, mobile phase composition was made to evaluate the impact on the method.

System suitability:

5 mg of Fexofenadine Hcl and 500 mg of Montelukast working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 100ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 20ml of diluent and sonicated to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**SYSTEM SUITABILITY****Table.2 Results for system suitability of Fexofenadine Hcl**

Injection	RT(min)	Peak area	TP	TF
1	2.5263	124652	1554.31	1.28
2	2.767	127376	1634.55	1.31
3	2.764	122803	1623.37	1.31
4	2.808	125382	1622.73	1.23
5	2.789	122153	1460.39	1.32
6	2.799	126345	1634.88	1.27
Mean		123634	-	-
SD		631.0	-	-
%RSD		0.6	-	-

Table.3 Results for system suitability of Montelukast

Injection	RT(min)	Peak area	TP	TF
1	3.901	434308	4315.31	1.17
2	4.016	436736	4232.73	1.17
3	4.012	436821	4372.54	1.17
4	4.140	435350	4354.17	1.17
5	4.077	425462	4322.22	1.17
6	4.056	438085	4328.19	1.18
Mean		44531.3	-	-
SD		1257.3	-	-
%RSD		0.3	-	-

ACCURACY:**Table 4: Accuracy results of Montelukast**

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount added(mg)	Amount found(mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	2332744	5	5.10	101.8%	100.5%
100%	3132697	10	9.99	99.9%	
150%	3918997	15	14.9	99.1%	

Table 5 Accuracy results of Fexofenadine Hcl

%Concentration(at specification level)	Area	Amount Added(mg)	Amount Found(mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	353867	5	5.0	101.3%	100.0%
100%	4735088	10	9.94	99.4%	
150%	5911798	15	14.8	99.2%	

PRECISION:**i) Repeatability****ii) Intermediate precision (Ruggedness)****Table 6 Accuracy results of Fexofenadine Hcl.**

Injection	Area
Injection-1	1501417
Injection-2	1486940
Injection-3	1490656
Injection-4	1487329
Injection-5	1490384
Average	1491345
Standard Deviation	5881.4
%RSD	0.39

Injection	Area
Injection-1	2235319
Injection-2	2240678
Injection-3	2249490
Injection-4	2245822
Injection-5	2251694
Average	2244601
Standard Deviation	6656.8
%RSD	0.32

Intermediate precision/Ruggedness**Table 7 Ruggedness results of Montelukast& Fexofenadine Hcl**

Injection	Area
Injection-1	2194758
Injection-2	2195700
Injection-3	2196191
Injection-4	2195326
Injection-5	2200951
Average	2196585
Standard Deviation	2496.0
%RSD	0.11

Injection	Area
Injection-1	1456296
Injection-2	1457422
Injection-3	1456513
Injection-4	1454579
Injection-5	1451483
Average	1455259
Standard Deviation	2347.6
%RSD	0.16

LINEARITY:**Fig 4 Chromatogram for Robustness more flow**

Fig. 5 Chromatogram for Robustness less flow

Table 8 System suitability results For Montelukast (Flow rate)

* Results for actual flow (1.0 ml/min) have been considered from Assay standard.

S.No	Flow Rate(ml/min)	System suitability results	
		USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	1748.5	1.22
2	1.0	1548.2	1.2
3	1.2	1948.0	1.2

System suitability results for Fexofenadine Hcl:

Table 9 System suitability results for Fexofenadine Hcl(Flow rate)

S.No	Flow Rate(ml/min)	System suitability results	
		USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	883.3	1.56
2	1.0	1234.0	1.1
3	1.2	969.2	1.6

B) Mobile Phase:

The Organic composition in the Mobile phase was varied from 70% to 60%. Standard solution 300 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Montelukast & 3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Fexofenadine Hcl was prepared and analyzed using the varied Mobile phase composition along with the actual mobile phase composition in the method.

Fig. 6 Chromatogram for Robustness more organic

Fig 7 Chromatogram for Robustness less organic

System suitability results for Montelukast:

Table 10 System suitability results for Montelukast (Mobile phase)

S.No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System suitability results	
		USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	10% Less	1748.5	1.22
2	Actual	1548.2	1.2
3	10% More	1948.0	1.2

System suitability results for Fexofenadine Hcl:

Table 11 System suitability results for Fexofenadine Hcl(Mobile phase)

S.No	Change in Organic Composition in the Mobile Phase	System suitability results	
		USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	10% Less	883.3	1.56
2	Actual	1234.0	1.1
3	10% More	969.2	1.6

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

A new method was established for simultaneous estimation of Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast by using Xterra C18 5 μ m (4.6*250mm) column, flow rate was 1ml/min, mobile phase ratio was Phosphate buffer (0.05M) pH 4.6: ACN (55:45% v/v) (pH was adjusted with orthophosphoric acid), detection wave length was 255nm. The instrument used was Shimadzu, model No. SPD-20MA LC+20AD, Software- LC-20 Solution. The retention times were found to be 2.399mins and 3.907mins. The % purity of Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast was found to be 100.7% and 101.4% respectively. The system suitability parameters for Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 1.3, 5117.5 and 1.4, 3877.3 the resolution was

found to be 8.0. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study for Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast was found in concentration range of 1 μ g-5 μ g and 100 μ g-500 μ g and correlation coefficient (r²) was found to be 0.999 and 0.999, % mean recovery was found to be 100% and 100.5%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.2 and 0.4, % RSD for intermediate precision was 0.5 and 0.1 respectively. The precision study was precise, robust, and repeatable. LOD value was 2.95 and 3.04, and LOQ value was 9.87 and 10 respectively. Hence the suggested RP-HPLC method can be used for routine analysis of Fexofenadine Hcl and Montelukast in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

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